

NATURAL FREQUENCY OF BI-STABLE COMPOSITE PLATES IN THERMAL ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The natural frequency of bi-stable cross-ply $[0_n/90_n]_T$ composite plates under thermomechanical loading is analysed theoretically. Based on Hamilton's principle, in conjunction with the Rayleigh-Ritz method, the analytical model with only 17 unknown terms is applied to predict the natural frequency of bi-stable composite plates. The properties of the composite material in current study are considered to be functions of temperature. The plate is subjected to two different thermal load, i.e. the uniform temperature field and through-thickness thermal gradient. The influence of this two temperature field on the natural frequency of the thin composite plates is predicted theoretically. Moreover, the predicted results are greatly affected by the uncertainty of uncertainties in geometry, material properties and the operating environment. The considered uncertainties include Young's moduli, Poisson's ratio and shear modulus, thermal expansion coefficients, ply thickness, density, cure and ambient temperature. The thermal effect and sensitivity to uncertainties are of great importance to the design and application of morphing structures manufactured from bi-stable composite plates.

1 INTRODUCTION

Bi-stable composite plates exhibit two stable static configurations and don't need continuous energy to maintain one stable configuration in Fig.1. The bi-stability of composite plates enables large deflections from one stable configuration to another with an appropriate triggering action. Bi-stable composite plates show a wide range of potential applications for morphing aircraft. Almost all related discussions are concentrated on cured shape and snap-through of bi-stable composite plates. Nevertheless, few studies focused attention on the free vibration of bi-stable composite plates. Vogl and Hyer [1] studied the natural frequencies of the 4-ply $[0_2/90_2]_T$ composite plates via the Rayleigh-Ritz model and the ABAQUS finite element package. They presented the fundamental frequency decreases with the increase of the side length. Samir[2] studied the snap-through load and natural frequency of bi-stable cross-ply $[0_4/90_4]_T$ composite laminates. He studied the laminate's length-to-thickness ratio is key to assess the existence of bi-stability. These models limit the curvature to be a constant which violates the boundary conditions near the free boundary. To fix that, Wu *et.al* [3] presented an analytical dynamic model with only 17 unknown terms is established based on Rayleigh's method and Hamilton's principle in this study. The analytical model accurately predicted the single-well and cross-well snap-through response when compared to the finite element and experimental results. The nonlinear dynamics of bi-stable plates confined to a single stable state has been experimentally studied by Arrieta *et.al* [4]. A simple model based on the observed results of two points is established, and captures the complex dynamic phenomenon of the tested bi-stable plates. Later, Arrieta *et.al* [5] presents that when the excitation frequency is close to the natural frequency of the stable configuration of bi-stable laminates, the excitation force required for the laminates to snap through is the minimum. However the model [4,5] cannot provide the overall response of the plate. Arrieta *et.al* [6] first established the linear model of the laminates and predicted their vibration modes, and then, on the basis of the predicted results of the linear model, the theoretical model of nonlinear dynamic response is obtained by using the Galerkin method. However, the unknown coefficients in the theoretical model are obtained by fitting the experimental results and have no practical physical significance. A Frouzian-Nejad *et.al* [7] scrutinize the static and dynamic responses of bi-stable hybrid

composite laminates, which are compared to bi-stable pure composite laminates. The work is validated experimentally. To the best of authors' knowledge, no previous work has been done on the thermomechanical analysis on the natural frequency of bi-stable cross-ply $[0n/90n]_T$ composite plates.

The natural frequency of bi-stable cross-ply $[0n/90n]_T$ composite plates are investigated under thermomechanical loading. Based on the Rayleigh-Ritz method, an analytical model with only 17 unknown terms is extended to predict the natural frequency of the thin composite plates, which are clamped at the centre point according to the classical lamination plate theory considering the von Karman geometric nonlinearity. The model is validated by experimental and finite element results. The material properties of the composite plates are considered to be a functions of temperature. The thin composite plates are subjected to two different kinds of thermal loads, i.e. the uniform temperature field and through-thickness thermal gradient. The influence of this two temperature field on the natural frequency of the thin composite plates is predicted analytically. Moreover, the predicted results are greatly affected by the uncertainty of uncertainties in geometry, material properties and the operating environment. The considered uncertainties include Young's moduli, Poisson's ratio and shear modulus, thermal expansion coefficients, ply thickness, density, cure and ambient temperature. The thermal effect and sensitivity to uncertainties are of great importance to the design and application of morphing structures manufactured from bi-stable composite plates.

2 THEORETICAL AND NUMERICAL METHODOLOGY

The study of thermal effect on the bi-stable behavior of bi-stable cross-ply $[0n/90n]_T$ composite plates is based on a combined theoretical-numerical methodology. As the material properties of the plate are affected by the temperature, bi-stable cross-ply $[0n/90n]_T$ composite plates investigated in this paper were made from T300/5028 graphite–epoxy composite with temperature-dependent material [8,9]. According to the experimental data [8,9] and then through fitting, material properties are presented as followed:

Material property	Value in T=20°C	Value with variation in temperature
Longitudinal Young's modulus, E_{11} (Pa)	1.4598×10^{11}	$5 \times 10^5 T^2 + 1.9 \times 10^7 T + 1.454 \times 10^{11}$
Transverse Young's modulus, E_{22} (Pa)	1.176×10^{10}	$1.2 \times 10^6 T^2 - 1.76 \times 10^8 T + 1.48 \times 10^{10}$
Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	0.3091	$4 \times 10^{-7} T^2 - 1.04 \times 10^{-3} T + 0.3297$
Shear modulus, G_{12} (Pa)	6.972×10^9	$-3 \times 10^4 T^2 - 7.3 \times 10^6 T + 7.13 \times 10^9$
Longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient, α_{11} ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	2.64×10^{-6}	$10^{-11} T^3 + 6 \times 10^{-10} T^2 - 1.88 \times 10^{-7} T + 6.08 \times 10^{-6}$
Transverse thermal expansion coefficient, α_{22} ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	2.65×10^{-5}	2.65×10^{-5}
Density ρ (kg/m ³)	1600	1600

Table 1: Material properties at room temperature and variation with temperature.

2.1 Theoretical analysis

The governed equations were derived by using the Hamilton's principle

$$\int_{t_0}^t \delta(\Pi - U) dt = 0 \quad (1)$$

where Π is the total kinetic energy and U is the total potential energy. The total potential energy of the plate under a thermal-induced load, U , can be given by

$$U = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{-\frac{L_x}{2}}^{\frac{L_x}{2}} \int_{-\frac{L_y}{2}}^{\frac{L_y}{2}} \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^T Q^{(k)} \varepsilon - \varepsilon^T Q^{(k)} \alpha^{(k)} (T - T_C) \right\} dz dy dx \quad (2)$$

where n is the number of layers within the laminate, $Q^{(k)}$ and $\alpha^{(k)}$ are transformed reduced stiffness matrix and thermal expansion coefficients vector in the k th layer, respectively. T and T_C are the cure and ambient temperature., respectively. L_x and L_y are the side lengths of the plate. h is the thickness of the laminate. The total strain vector ε is described as following

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon^0 + z\kappa = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} + z \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 \\ \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \\ \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \end{Bmatrix} + z \begin{Bmatrix} -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \\ -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \\ -2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where ε^0 and κ are the mid-plane strains and curvatures of the laminate. u^0 , v^0 and w are the displacements of a point on the mid-plane laminate in the x -, y - and z -directions, respectively, which can be defined based on Rayleigh–Ritz method.

According to the previous model [3], the out-of-plate displacement and mid-plane strains are given by

$$\begin{aligned} w(t) &= a(t)x^2 + b(t)y^2 + a_1(t)x^4 + b_1(t)y^4 + a_2(t)x^6 + b_2(t)y^6 + e(t)x^2y^2 \\ \varepsilon_x^0(t) &= c(t) + c_1(t)y^2 + c_2(t)y^4 + c_3(t)y^6 + c_4(t)x^2y^2 + B_{11}^* \kappa_x + B_{12}^* \kappa_y + A^{-1} N_{s1}^T \\ \varepsilon_y^0(t) &= d(t) + d_1(t)x^2 + d_2(t)x^4 + d_3(t)x^6 + d_4(t)x^2y^2 - B_{12}^* \kappa_x - B_{11}^* \kappa_y + A^{-1} N_{s1}^T \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where A and B are the stretching stiffness matrix and the stretching-bending coupling matrix, respectively. N_{s1} is the first entry of the resultant force vector due to the thermal stress. B_{11}^* and B_{12}^* are the (1,1) and (1,2) entries of $-A^{-1}B$, respectively. The unknown coefficients, $a_i(t)$, $b_i(t)$, $c_i(t)$, $d_i(t)$ and $e(t)$, represent generalized co-ordinates in the model.

According to the principle of minimum potential energy, the partial derivative of the total potential energy with respect to the unknown coefficients can be taken to obtain algebraic equations with respect to the 17 unknown parameters. Then the stable configuration of the laminae can be obtained by solving the equations. The result of the stable configuration is used as the initial value of w , who is renamed w^0 . The mid-plane strains ε^0 are rewritten as following

$$\varepsilon^0 = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} + \frac{w^0}{R_x} \\ \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} + \frac{w^0}{R_y} \\ \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The total kinetic energy of the plate Π can be calculated in the z direction as

$$\Pi = \int_{-\frac{L_x}{2}}^{\frac{L_x}{2}} \int_{-\frac{L_y}{2}}^{\frac{L_y}{2}} \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \frac{1}{2} \rho (\dot{u}^2 + \dot{v}^2 + \dot{w}^2) dz dy dx \quad (6)$$

where $u = u^0 - z \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x}$, $v = v^0 - z \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial y}$ and $w = w^0$.

Using equations (2), (5) and (6) in equation (1) leads to the dynamic equations of the bi-stable composite plates. For the nontrivial solution, the frequency equations can be given and solved in order to obtain the natural frequency.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As the bi-stable plate has the potential in the application in the morphing wing of aircraft, it can be influenced by both of uniform temperature field and through-thickness thermal gradient. Considering the thermal influence is made up of three parts, a linear through-thickness temperature variation given

by

$$T = T_0 + \Delta T + zT_z \quad (7)$$

where T_0 is the room temperature (20°C), ΔT is the variation of uniform temperature field, and T_z is the through-thickness thermal gradient.

To validate the accuracy of the theoretical model, the predicted natural frequencies are compared with the experimental and finite element results available in the literature. The fundamental vibration frequency is of great importance since it exhibits the majority of the energy of the system. Table 2 shows the fundamental frequency of the 4-ply and the 6-ply laminates for specific sizes. The predicted frequency using the theoretical model was found to be in good agreement with the experimental results of [1,3].

Laminate length(mm)	4-ply Laminate			6-ply Laminate	
	ABAQUS Ref.[1]	Experiments Ref.[3]	Current Model	Experiments Ref.[3]	Current Model
153	65.8		70.00		
100		25.5	25.84	42	45.24

Table 2: Natural frequency in Hz of the 4-ply and 6-ply laminates for specific sizes.

3.1 Uniform temperature field

Assuming T_0 is 20°C, T_z is 0°C and only variation of uniform temperature field ΔT is considered in this case. According to working situation and material's limit of the bi-stable plate, the range of temperature T is chosen from -150°C to 120 °C, which means ΔT varies from -170°C to 100 °C. The theoretical prediction of ΔT on the natural frequency in the stable state is shown in Figure 1. Natural frequency is equal to 34.4385 Hz when environmental temperature remains unchanged. The natural frequency decreases linearly until ΔT reaching 40 °C from which it begins increase gradually. When temperature dependence is not considered, the natural frequency increases with ΔT , but its amplitude is smaller. Therefore, the influence of temperature dependence characteristic cannot be ignored on natural frequency of the bi-stable plate.

Figure 1: The influence of the uniform temperature field on the natural frequency of this plates

3.2 Through-thickness temperature

This section is to study the influence of through-thickness thermal gradient on natural frequency of the bi-stable plate. In order to match the actual working conditions, the mid-plane temperature is chosen as 20°C, and the through-thickness thermal gradient T_z is assumed to range from -20 °C/mm to 20 °C/mm along the thickness direction. The impacts of T_z on the natural frequency of the bi-stable plate are shown in Figure 2 from which we can see that natural frequency varies symmetrically about $T_z = 0$ °C/mm between two configurations. When temperature dependence is not considered, the linear

behavior is obvious on the impacts of T_z on the natural frequency of the bi-stable plate. However, when temperature dependence is considered, the curvatures follow a non-linear trend with respect to the through-thickness temperature T_z .

Figure 2: The influence of through-thickness thermal gradient on the natural frequency of this plates
3.3 Sensitivity analysis

A summary of the sensitivities of the natural frequency to $\pm 10\%$ change in each of the properties is shown in Table 3. From these results it is clear that variations in material properties and environmental conditions can have a significant effect on natural frequency. The uncertainties can be a major source of discrepancies between analytical models and the experimental results. The model is observed to be most sensitive to the Young's moduli (E_{11} and E_{22}), ply thickness (t) and density (ρ). Special care should be taken in characterizing these critical parameters to minimize the uncertainties and improve confidence in the model prediction.

Variable	Configuration (%)		Frequency (%)	
	-10%	+10%	-10%	+10%
E_{11} (Pa)	4.63	-4.33	-2.79	2.70
E_{22} (Pa)	-4.68	4.10	-2.24	2.17
ν_{12}	0.643	-0.649	-0.094	0.101
G_{12} (Pa)	-0.117	0.101	-0.049	0.051
α_{11} ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	1.22	-1.22	-0.048	0.048
α_{22} ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	-12.2	12.3	0.488	-0.472
t (mm)	13.4	-10.8	-10.62	10.68
$T-T_0$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	-11.0	11.0	0.439	-
ρ (kg/m^3)	—	—	5.41	4.65

Table 3: Maximum change in natural frequency for a $\pm 10\%$ variation in each design variable.

The previous section has identified that accurate characterization of laminate properties, dimensions and ambient conditions can minimize errors between analytical models and experimental measurements of bi-stable laminates in laboratory conditions. However, in practical applications it is reasonable to expect large variations in the operating temperature. Therefore in this section the effects of large temperature change and the subsequent changes in material properties with temperature (Table 1) are considered. The coupled effect of using temperature dependent material properties with a $\pm 10\%$ change in temperature from cure to room temperature (20°C) will be initially considered: corresponding to a $2\text{--}38^{\circ}\text{C}$ ambient temperature range. The effect of the temperature dependency of each material property on natural frequency will be considered to identify which have the largest effect

on natural frequency. Clearly E_{22} is the property most sensitive to temperature for this particular material system.

Variable temperature	Configuration (%)		Frequency (%)	
	-10%	+10%	-10%	+10%
Temperature change only	-11.0	11.0	0.439	-0.426
All	-9.33	4.55	-3.16	4.39
E_{11} (Pa)	-11.2	11.2	0.581	-0.519
E_{22} (Pa)	-17.3	19.6	-2.94	3.80
ν_{12}	-10.7	10.7	0.388	-0.373
G_{12} (Pa)	-11.0	9.33	0.428	-0.417
α_{11} ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	-2.35	-2.68	0.094	0.107

Table 4: Maximum change in natural frequency for a $\pm 10\%$ change in temperature change

9 CONCLUSIONS

Thermal effect on the natural frequency of bi-stable cross-ply [0n/90n]T composite plates is analysed theoretically. Both of the uniform temperature field and through-thickness thermal gradients have a significant effect on natural frequency of bi-stable cross-ply composite plates. The influence of temperature dependence characteristic cannot be ignored on natural frequency of the bi-stable plate. Moreover, the predicted results are greatly affected by the uncertainty of uncertainties in geometry, material properties and the operating environment. When temperature dependence is not considered, the Young's moduli (E_{11} and E_{22}), ply thickness (t) and density (ρ) are most sensitive on the natural frequency of bi-stable cross-ply composite plates. When temperature dependence is considered, E_{22} is the property most sensitive to temperature for this particular material system. Special care should be taken in characterizing these critical parameters to minimize the uncertainties and improve confidence in the model prediction. Therefore, the theoretical and numerical analysis of thermal effect on the natural frequency of the bi-stable plates in this paper is expected to provide a prediction for the design, manufacture and application of the bi-stable composite structures.

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